

XORIJY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

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USING INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES : ON THE EXAMPLE OF JAPAN TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Annotation: *The role of using modern technology devices in current academic life and its effects on students' learning style, motivation and participation are explored in this article. As well as, this paper is dedicated to highlighting an example of technology -based method in teaching English language in Japan. Just like a coin two sides, technology-based teaching approach has not only a good, but also a bad influence on students' academic knowledge and behaviour. While advancing soft skills , such as verbal communication, critical thinking and knowledge retention, the modern robots has many side-effects , including technical distrubtions, lack of respect for human teachers and over-reliance on AI.*

Key words: *innovative , technology, learning English, foreign languages, Japan , robots, methods, education, smartphone, computer, online education, integrating technology ,visual classrooms ,cost-effective, wide data-base, artificial intelligence.*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqola zamonaviy o'quv hayotida zamonaviy texnologik qurilmalardan foydalanishning o'rni va ularning talabalarning o'rganish uslubi, motivatsiyasi va faolligiga ta'sirini o'rganadi. Bundan tashqari, ushbu maqola Yaponiyada ingliz tilini o'qitishda texnologiyaga asoslangan usulning namunasini ko'rsatishga bag'ishlangan. Tanganing ikki tomoni bo'lgani kabi, texnologiya asosida o'rganishga yondashuv talabalarning akademik bilimi va xulq-atvoriga ham yaxshi, ham yomon ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Og'zaki muloqot, tanqidiy fikrlash va bilimlarni saqlash kabi yumshoq ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirish bilan birga, zamonaviy robotlar ko'plab nojo'ya ta'sirlarga ega, jumladan, texnik nosozliklar, inson o'qituvchilarini hurmat qilmaslik va AIga haddan tashqari qaramlik.*

Kalit so'zlar: *innovatsion, texnologiya, ingliz tilini o'rganish, xorijiy tillar, Yaponiya, robotlar, usullar, ta'lim, smartfon, kompyuter, onlayn ta'lim, texnologiya integratsiyasi, vizual sinflar, tejamkor, keng ma'lumotlar bazasi, sun'iy intellekt.*

Аннотация: *В этой статье рассматривается роль использования современных технологических устройств в современной академической жизни и их влияние на стиль обучения, мотивацию и участие студентов. Кроме того, эта статья посвящена освещению примера технологического метода в преподавании английского языка в Японии. Подобно двум сторонам монеты, технологический подход к обучению оказывает не только хорошее, но и плохое влияние на академические знания и поведение студентов. При развитии гибких навыков, таких как вербальное общение, критическое мышление и сохранение знаний,*

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современные роботы имеют много побочных эффектов, включая технические помехи, отсутствие уважения к учителям-людям и чрезмерную зависимость от ИИ.

Ключевые слова: *инновационный, технология, изучение английского языка, иностранные языки, Япония, роботы, методы, образование, смартфон, компьютер, онлайн-образование, интеграция технологий, визуальные классы, экономически эффективный, широкая база данных, искусственный интеллект.*

Introduction

The modern development of education has given rise to a new direction of innovative pedagogy. “Innovative” translated from English means the introduction (dissemination) of innovation, which implies a departure from previous patterns, the use of new approaches and ways of thinking. The socio-psychological aspect of innovation was developed by the American Researcher E. Rogers. According to some scientists, “innovation” means a tool, a new method, methodology, technology [1 p. 35]. Using technological advancement (smartphones, computers, interactive boards, artificial intelligence) in the field of education has opened the door to many opportunities in the study of foreign languages.

Today, the process of informatization is an important mechanism for improving the education system, while it is aimed at improving the quality of education, its accessibility and efficiency. Information culture acts as a key factor in social development, and innovative technologies in the study of a foreign language make it possible to develop the individual abilities of students, enhance the activity of cognition, and also create a culture of an innovative nature. To solve existing problems, various types of innovative technologies are used (technology for complete assimilation of knowledge, multi-level training, technology of an adaptive learning system, modular training, etc.), without which modern education cannot be imagined [3].

The role of utilizing innovative technologies in education system.

How important is technology in education? It played a crucial role during The COVID-19 pandemic and demonstrated why online education should be a vital part of teaching and learning with the assist of technological advancements in terms of online plarforms, like ZOOM.

By integrating technology into existing curricula, as opposed to using it solely as a crisis-management tool, teachers can harness online learning as a powerful educational tool. The effective use of digital learning tools in classrooms can increase student engagement, help teachers improve their lesson plans, and facilitate

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personalized learning. It also helps students build essential 21st-century skills. Virtual classrooms, video, augmented reality (AR), robots, and other technology tools can not only make class more lively, they can also create more inclusive learning environments that foster collaboration and inquisitiveness and enable teachers to collect data on student performance.[2]

Robots to help teach English in Japanese classrooms.

The Japanese government has announced plans to use robots in school classrooms as part of a new approach to improve its population's English proficiency, and take advantage of an expected increase in tourism. Rolling out in 2019, the trial will see robots implemented in 500 schools throughout Japan, and join a number already using the technology as part of their curriculum.

Students will be able to converse with the robots, which Kaneshiro, who works as the director of the office for promoting foreign language education, said would alleviate some of the pressures of in-person delivery.

Speaking with *The PIE News*, he added that the robots would improve students' listening, reading, speaking and writing skills, and would be used in conjunction with other technologies, including study apps. It is confirmed that students can learn efficiently and pronounce without hesitation by using a robot independently or in smaller numbers of students.

The robots would also help in regions with lower numbers of assistant language teachers and remote areas with insufficient management systems, he added.[4]

Advantages of Robot Teachers

1. Wide Knowledge

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One of the main dominant sides of robots is owning a wide range of data-base compared to human teachers. Given that robots are programmed to enable them to deliver their teaching roles, the information that you want to be transferred to pupils in the class can be inputted into the robot without limitation. The extensive knowledge base is vital as it enables the robots to provide a solution to students' problems and helps further their educational careers.

2. Non-Irrelevant Conversations

The utilization of robots as teachers in the classroom prevent the elimination of lots of off-topic discussions in the classroom. The number of irrelevant discussions that take place usually in the presence of human teachers is so dumbfounding. The robot cannot be diverted, caught off guard, or distracted from the lesson ongoing. Students gain more knowledge by spending class hours usefully without any distractions.

3. Patience

The robots cannot get exhausted while they are conducting lessons. Because of the fact that they do not have feelings, they cannot feel the same as human beings. Hence, they cannot become impatient or intolerant of students. They stay kind, and patient, and are receptive to any queries regardless of whatever it is that is happening in the classrooms.

4. Cost-Effective

There is no need to pay robots. They just teach according to how they have been programmed. Because of this side, they might replace humans in near future.

5. Boosting soft skills

By being in contact with robot instructors, pupils improve their verbal communication, problem- solving skills and critical thinking as well. Because of the fact that robots have a special system for expressing words like native speakers, students learn how to pronounce words fluently and correctly with ease.

Disadvantages of Robot Teachers

1. Technical Disruptions

Everything mechanical has no guarantee of non-breakage. Hence, the robot, being mechanically designed can break down at any time and cause a great disruption to learning. Only individuals with expertise can repair a malfunctioned robot. Hence, it may take days or weeks for a broken robot to be repaired. That way, a great deal of time gets wasted waiting for the robot to be back to shape. Also, in the event of a system breakdown in the robot, a lot of information can be lost. Hence, this may

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necessitate the reprogramming of the robot to get it back to its original functioning state.

2. Lack of Respect for Teachers

Students may show disrespect to the robot instructors as they are not human. The robots may have a difficulty in trying to keep students under the control. Students may accept the whole robot teaching as a joke.

3. High-quality Infrastructure in the Classrooms

Robots require high-quality systems to function properly. There should be electricity and internet connections to facilitate their functioning. While there are still some problems with electricity and low connection in some places, it is impossible to provide robot mentors in full.

4. Dependency on Artificial Intelligence

Over-reliance on AI for decision-making and problem-solving can diminish critical thinking and creative abilities.

Conclusion

In conclusion, technological advancements present both challenges and opportunities. By thoughtfully implementing robot-based education, we can encourage students to participate more actively in learning process, as they possess more functions which attracts students with several teaching methods, activities, rewards and wide knowledge. In addition to this, we can conclude that this approach has a good impact on enhancing critical thinking, problem-solving skill and fluency. Despite the fact that they have various downsides, robots are commonly used in education due to their efficiency.

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